

Operator ID: fb209
Sample ID: 70/100
Sample Weight: 12.570 mg

70/100: 70-100-1-1.ds8d
Heat Flow Endo Up (mW) : Step: 1
70/100: 70-100-1-1.ds8d
Heat Flow Endo Up (mW) : Step: 2
70/100: 70-100-1-2.ds8d
Heat Flow Endo Up (mW) : Step: 1

Funktionspolymere 209

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1) Heat from -100.00°C to 70.00°C at 20.00°C/min